

Einstein's Notational Equation of Electro-Magnetic Field Equation in Rindler spacetime

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Abstract: We find Einstein's notational equation of the electro-magnetic field equation and the electro-magnetic field in Rindler space-time. Because, electromagnetic fields of the accelerated frame include in general relativity theory.

Keywords: The general relativity theory, The Rindler spacetime, Einstein's notational equation

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1. INTRODUCTION

Our article's aim is that we find Einstein notation's equations in general relativity theory instead of the electro-magnetic field equations in Rindler space-time.

Rindler coordinate are

$$ct = \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right)$$

$$x = \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right) - \frac{c^2}{a_0}, y = \xi^2, z = \xi^3 \quad (1) \text{ The electro-magnetic}$$

field equation is in Rindler space-time [1].

$$\nabla_{\xi}^{\rho} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{\xi}^{\rho} = 4\pi\rho_{\xi} \left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right) \quad (2-i)$$

$$\frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)} \nabla_{\xi}^{\rho} \times \left\{ \mathbf{B}_{\xi}^{\rho} \left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right) \right\} = \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)} \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}_{\xi}^{\nu}}{c \partial \xi^0} + \frac{4\pi}{c} \mathbf{J}_{\xi}^{\rho} \quad (2-ii)$$

$$\nabla_{\xi}^{\nu} \cdot \mathbf{B}_{\xi}^{\nu} = 0 \quad (2-iii)$$

$$\frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)} \nabla_{\xi}^{\rho} \times \left\{ \mathbf{E}_{\xi}^{\rho} \left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right) \right\} = - \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}\right)} \frac{\partial \mathbf{B}_{\xi}^{\nu}}{c \partial \xi^0} \quad (2-iv)$$

$$\mathbf{E}_{\xi}^{\rho} = (E_{\xi^1}, E_{\xi^2}, E_{\xi^3}), \mathbf{B}_{\xi}^{\nu} = (B_{\xi^1}, B_{\xi^2}, B_{\xi^3}), \nabla_{\xi}^{\rho} = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^1}, \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^2}, \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^3}\right)$$

The Electro-magnetic field $(\vec{E}_\xi, \vec{B}_\xi)$ is defined in Rindler spacetime [1].

$$\vec{E}_\xi = -\frac{1}{(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2})} \nabla_\xi \{ \phi_\xi (1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2})^2 \} - \frac{1}{(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2})} \frac{\partial \vec{A}_\xi}{c \partial \xi^0}$$

$$\vec{B}_\xi = \nabla_\xi \times \vec{A}_\xi$$

In this time, $\nabla_\xi = (\frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^1}, \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^2}, \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^3})$, $\vec{A}_\xi = (A_{\xi^1}, A_{\xi^2}, A_{\xi^3})$ (3)

2. EINSTEIN'S NOTATIONAL EQUATION IN GENERAL RELATIVITY THEORY

Electromagnetic field tensor $F_\xi^{\mu\nu}$ is in Rindler space-time,

$$F_\xi^{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & E_{\xi^1} & E_{\xi^2} & E_{\xi^3} \\ -E_{\xi^1} & 0 & (1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2})B_{\xi^3} & -(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2})B_{\xi^2} \\ -E_{\xi^2} & -(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2})B_{\xi^3} & 0 & (1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2})B_{\xi^1} \\ -E_{\xi^3} & (1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2})B_{\xi^2} & -(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2})B_{\xi^1} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Electromagnetic field tensor $F_{\xi\mu\nu}$ is in Rindler space-time,

$$F_{\xi\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2})E_{\xi^1} & -(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2})E_{\xi^2} & -(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2})E_{\xi^3} \\ (1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2})E_{\xi^1} & 0 & B_{\xi^3} & -B_{\xi^2} \\ (1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2})E_{\xi^2} & -B_{\xi^3} & 0 & B_{\xi^1} \\ (1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2})E_{\xi^3} & B_{\xi^2} & -B_{\xi^1} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Hence, Eq(3) is

$$F_{\xi\mu\nu} = \frac{\partial A_{\xi^\nu}}{\partial \xi^\mu} - \frac{\partial A_{\xi^\mu}}{\partial \xi^\nu}, \quad A_{\xi^\mu} = (1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2})^2 \phi_\xi, \quad \vec{A}_\xi \quad (6)$$

Eq(2-i),Eq(2-ii),Eq(2-iii),Eq(2-iv) are

$$F_{\xi}^{\mu\nu},_{,\nu} = \frac{4\pi}{c} j^\mu (1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2}) \quad (7-i)$$

$$F_{\xi\mu\nu,\lambda} + F_{\xi\nu\lambda,\mu} + F_{\xi\lambda\mu,\nu} = 0 \quad (7-ii)$$

Hence, the Lagrangian L_ξ of electromagnetic field in Rindler space-time is,

$$L_\xi = -\frac{1}{4} F_\xi^{\mu\nu} F_{\xi\mu\nu}$$

$$= -\frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{a_0 \xi^1}{c^2} \right) \mathcal{B}_\xi^2 - E_\xi^2, \\ \overset{\mathcal{U}}{E}_\xi = (E_{\xi^1}, E_{\xi^2}, E_{\xi^3}), \overset{\mathcal{U}}{B}_\xi = (B_{\xi^1}, B_{\xi^2}, B_{\xi^3}), \left| \overset{\mathcal{U}}{E}_\xi \right| = E_\xi, \left| \overset{\mathcal{U}}{B}_\xi \right| = B_\xi \quad (8)$$

3. CONCLUSION

We find Einstein's notational equations of the electro-magnetic field equation in uniformly accelerated frame.

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